

The Influence of Celebrity Endorser Variables on Brand Image

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Celebrity Endorsers, Brand Image, Skintific

Received : 4 June

Revised : 17 June

Accepted : 23 July

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ABSTRACT

This research aims to determine the effect of Celebrity Endorser Variables on Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City). The population in this study were all consumers of Skintific products in Madiun City. The research sample is part of the consumers of Skintific products in Madiun City, totaling 100 people. Data was obtained using a questionnaire. The sampling technique in this study used probability sampling and simple random sampling methods. Hypothesis testing using multiple linear regression analysis with the help of the SPSS 22 program. The result obtained is that the existence of Celebrity Endorsers will build or maintain Brand Image to customers. So the better a public figure in becoming a telada, the higher the Brand Image in the eyes of customers.

INTRODUCTION

Competition in the industrial world is so intense that it requires the readiness of industry players to deal with it. This development has a positive impact and a negative impact on the industry. The positive impact is in the form of opportunities which are expected to provide benefits for business people. Meanwhile, the negative impact will affect industrial activities if industry players do not have creativity and innovation in developing their industry so that it can harm their business.

According to Philip Kotler, consumers are all individuals and households who buy or acquire goods or services for personal consumption (Kotler, P., dan Armstrong, 2012) (Kotler, 2010)(Kotler,P & Keller, 2012) (Kotler, P., dan Keller, 2016). Currently, consumers are quite smart in choosing a product. Before consumers finally decide to choose a product, consumers will think about several things, namely product quality, product price, usability, endorsers used by the company and the brand image owned by the product.

Endorsers are certain icons or figures that are often referred to as direct sources to deliver a message and or demonstrate a product or service in promotional activities that aim to support the effectiveness of delivering product messages to consumers with the aim of attracting consumers so that consumers have different perceptions. The use of endorsers or better known as opinion leaders is more effective in product promotion activities. Humans tend to imitate what is done by someone who is considered to have advantages over themselves. The use of the right endorser as a supporter of an advertisement is able to influence and get consumer attention that the product has high quality (Ningsih et al., 2021)(et al., 2018)(Saparso et al., 2021). A brand image is part of a brand that can be recognized but cannot be spoken, such as a symbol, letter design or special color, or customer perception of a product or service represented by the brand(Tamara et al., 2021)(Tsabitah et al., 2021).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Between Celebrity Endorser and Brand Image has a relationship where celebrities have a positive meaning for consumers because they build themselves through a career journey and also manage their lives in the public eye carefully"(Annissa et al., 2021)(Arifiya et al., 2021)(Suminto et al., 2022).

The effectiveness of a celebrity endorsement depends not only on the public's perception of the expertise, trustworthiness, and attractiveness and gender of the celebrity starring in the ad. Its effectiveness also depends on the type of ad it stars in. This means that the effectiveness of celebrities as advertising stars or endorsers depends on the synergistic relationship or compatibility of the brand being supported and the celebrity endorser(Natalia Santoso, 2018)(Firmanza et al., 2022).

"The effectiveness of celebrity endorser support for advertising a product is not only from its personality in the form of attractiveness and credibility but also a match with the product being advertised. In addition to a suitable personality, it is also related to the character of the product itself"(Firman et al., 2021)(Freire et al., 2018).

Based on the problems described, the hypothesis in the research is as follows:

Ho : It is suspected that there is no influence between the Celebrity Endorser Variable and Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City).

Ha : It is suspected that there is an influence between the Celebrity Endorser variable on Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City).

Figure 1. Framework of Thought

Based on Figure 1 above, it can be described that the independent variable consisting of Celebrity Endorser (X), affects the dependent variable, namely Brand Image (Y), in this case, users of the Skecher brand shoes in the Madiun City area.

METHODOLOGY

This research is a quantitative research that tests the hypothesis about the influence of the Celebrity Endorser Variable on Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City). In this study, the focus of the analysis unit is the people who buy Skintific products in Madiun City. The research setting in this study is the field. The time dimension of the data is cross section, namely data collection at a certain time with many samples.

Definisi Operasional dan Pengukuran Variabel

Free Variable (X) : Celebrity Endorser

"Celebrity endorsers are celebrities, especially from the entertainment business or sports fields are a staple of North American advertising. This is understandable because as many consumers as possible identify with these stars, often by viewing them as heroes for their achievements, personality and physical attractiveness".

Dependent Variable: Brand Image (Y)

According to Keller (1993) in his journal entitled "Copeptualizing Measuring and Managing Customer - Based Brand Equity" there are three major classifications of associations that form a brand image, namely attributes, benefits, and attitudes.

The analysis technique used in the research is descriptive statistical test, data quality test, classical assumption test and hypothesis testing.

RESULT

Description of Research Variables

The description analysis in the study is presented by presenting the research data which includes the minimum value, maximum value, mean, and standard deviation of each variable. The following is a description of each research variable:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistical Test Results

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>Celebrity Endorser (X)</i>	100	26	60	42,86	7,642
<i>Citra Merek (Y)</i>	100	24	49	39,08	4,773

Table 1. shows that :

a. Of the 100 respondents, the *Celebrity Endorser (X)* variable has a minimum value of 26, a maximum value of 60, an average of 42.86, and a standard deviation of 7.642. The *Celebrity Endorser (X)* variable uses 12 statement items so that the average item is 42.86 divided by 12 items equal to 3.571 from a Likert scale of 1 to 5. This average shows that the *Celebrity Endorser (X)* variable is classified as high, meaning that users of Skintific products in Madiun City are quite high with the *Celebrity Endorser (X)*.

b. Of the 100 respondents, the *Brand Image variable (Y)* has a minimum value of 24, a maximum value of 49, an average of 39.08, and a standard deviation of 4.773. The *Brand Image variable (Y)* uses 10 statement items so that the average item is 39.08 divided by 10 items equal to 3.908 from a Likert scale of 1 to 5. This average shows that *Brand Image (Y)* is classified as high, meaning that the *Brand Image (Y)* of Skintific products in Madiun City is quite high.

Data Quality Test

Validity Test

The data tested were 100 respondents using SPSS 22.0. The following are the results of the validity test:

Table 2. Results of Validity Test

<i>Celebrity Endorser (X)</i>					
<i>Item</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Keterangan</i>	<i>Item</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Keterangan</i>
1	0,001	Valid	7	0,001	Valid
2	0,001	Valid	8	0,001	Valid
3	0,001	Valid	9	0,001	Valid
4	0,001	Valid	10	0,001	Valid
5	0,001	Valid	11	0,001	Valid
6	0,001	Valid	12	0,001	Valid
<i>Citra Merek (Y)</i>					
<i>Item</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Keterangan</i>	<i>Item</i>	<i>Sig (2-tailed)</i>	<i>Keterangan</i>
1	0,001	Valid	6	0,001	Valid
2	0,001	Valid	7	0,001	Valid
3	0,001	Valid	8	0,001	Valid
4	0,001	Valid	9	0,001	Valid
5	0,001	Valid	10	0,001	Valid

The results of the validity calculation show that the statement items for the Celebrity Endorser and Brand Image variables are declared all valid because they have a Sig (2-tailed) value of less than 0.05 and a corrected item total correlation greater than rtable (0.1966).

Reliability Test

Table 3. Reliability Test Result

Variabel	jumlah item pernyataan	Cronbach's Alpha	Keterangan
Celebrity Endorser (X)	12	0,852	Reliabel
Citra Merek (Y)	10	0,828	Reliabel

The results of the Celebrity Endorser and Brand Image variable reliability test show that Cronbach's Alpha > 0.6. Thus the research variables are declared reliable and can then be used in research.

Classical Assumption Test

Normality Test

Figure 2. Normality Test Plot Diagram

Based on the normality test output above, the data (points) spread around the diagonal line and follow the direction of the diagonal line, so the regression model fulfills the assumption of normality.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Results

Mode 1	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Celebrity Endorser (X)	1,000	1,000

Based on the multicollinearity test output table 4 shows that the results of the calculation of the tolerance value of each independent variable, namely Celebrity Endorser (X) = 1.000; which obtained a tolerance value > 0.10 which means there is no correlation between the independent variables. The results of the VIF calculation of each independent variable, namely Celebrity Endorser (X) = 1.000; obtained the results of the VIF value < than 10. So it can be concluded

that there is no multicollinearity between the independent variables in the regression model.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the scatterplot graph, it shows that the points spread randomly and are spread both above and below the number 0 on the Y axis and none of them form a certain regular pattern (Ghozali, 2005). This means that there is no heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Autocorrelation Test

Table 5. Results of Autocorrelation Test Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.316 ^a	.100	.091	4.551	1.758

a. Predictors: (Constant), SUM_X

b. Dependent Variable: SUM_Y

Based on table 5, the Durbin-Watson value in the regression model is 1.758 with a significant level of 0.05 (5%) with a total research sample of (N) 100 and the number of independent variables 1 (K = 1), the dL value is 1.654 and dU is 1.694. So the DW value is greater than the dL limit and less than dU or (1.654 < 1.694 < 1.758), so it can be concluded that there is no autocorrelation in the equation.

Then testing with the run test is carried out because the previous test is not convincing whether autocorrelation occurs or not. The results of the run test are presented in table 5.

Table 6. Test Results Runs Test

	<i>Unstandardized Residual</i>
<i>Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)</i>	0,027

From the run test conducted, the Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) 0.027 > 0.05. Based on the test results, it indicates that there is no negative or positive autocorrelation problem.

Hypothesis Test

Table 7. Multiple Linear Regression Test Results
 Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	30.621	2.606		11.753	.000		
	SUM_X	.197	.060	.316	3.297	.001	1.000	1.000

Dependent Variable: SUM_Y

Table 7 can be explained as follows:

$$Y = 30,621 LP + 0,197 PCB$$

Constant = 30.621; meaning that if the Celebrity Endorser variable (X) is zero, then the value of Brand Image (Y) is 30.621. The regression coefficient (β_1) is 0.197 positive direction; meaning that if there is an increase in the Celebrity Endorser variable (X) by one unit, the Brand Image (Y) also increases by 0.197 one unit.

Based on hypothesis testing with the t test, it is known that the Celebrity Endorser variable (X) has a tcount value of 3.297 with a significant level of 0.000 ($0.000 < 0.05$), this means that the Celebrity Endorser variable (X) has a positive influence on Brand Image (Y).

DISCUSSION

Celebrity Endorser (X) has an effect on Brand Image (Y) Based on the results of the t test, it is known that the Celebrity Endorser variable (X) has a tcount value of 3.297 with a significant level of 0.001 ($0.00 < 0.05$). This means that the hypothesis (H) is accepted, this means that there is an influence between the Celebrity Endorser variable on Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City).

With the Celebrity Endorser will build or maintain Brand Image to customers. So the better a public figure in becoming a telada, the higher the Brand Image in the eyes of customers.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the description that has been presented, it can be concluded that Celebrity Endorser in this study has a significance value of 0.001 < 0.05 so it can be concluded that Celebrity Endorser has a positive effect on Brand Image (Study on Skintific Product Users in Madiun City).

SUGGESTION

Some of the limitations identified in this study include:

1. The independent variables used in this study are only limited to the Celebrity Endorser variable, while there are still many other independent variables such as Product Quality, Service Quality, Advertising, Price, etc.
2. The scope of research is limited to users of Skintific products in Madiun City.
3. The samples taken in this study were only 100 samples of Skintific product users in Madiun City.

REFERENCES

- Annissa, A. N., & Paramita, E. L. (2021). Brand Promotion: The Effects of Celebrity Endorsement and Brand Image on Consumer Buying Decision. *Jurnal Bisnis Dan Manajemen*, 8(1), 82–90. doi: 10.26905/jbm.v8i1.5413
- Arifiya, N. A., Prasasty, A. T. P. T., & Nurhidayati, R. N. (2021). Analysis Of The Effect Of Brand Image On The Sales Volume Of Three Products. *E-Mabis: Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 22(1), 25–30. doi: 10.29103/e-mabis.v22i1.646
- Firman, A., Ilyas, G. B., Reza, H. K., Lestari, S. D., & Putra, A. H. P. K. (2021). The Mediating Role of Customer Trust on the Relationships of Celebrity Endorsement and E-WOM to Instagram Purchase Intention. *Jurnal Minds: Manajemen Ide Dan Inspirasi*, 8(1), 107. doi: 10.24252/minds.v8i1.20594
- Firmanza, M. H. D., & Artanti, Y. (2022). Online Buying Intentions of Shopee Consumers: the Influence of Celebrity Endorsement, Social Media Marketing, and Brand Image. *Jurnal Manajemen Pemasaran*, 16(2), 87–95. doi: 10.9744/pemasaran.16.2.87-95
- Freire, O., Quevedo-Silva, F., Senise, D., & Scrivano, P. (2018). The effectiveness of celebrity endorsement in aspiring new celebrities: Examining the effects of brand, congruence, charisma and overexposure. *RAUSP Management Journal*, 53(3), 289–303. doi: 10.1108/RAUSP-04-2018-011
- Indarto, E. W., Suroso, I., Sudaryanto, S., & Qomariah, N. (2018). the Effect of Brand Image and Product Attributes on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. *Jurnal Aplikasi Manajemen*, 16(3), 457–466. doi: 10.21776/ub.jam.2018.016.03.10
- Kotler, P., dan Armstrong, G. (2012). *Principles Of Marketing (14th Editi)*. United States: Pearson Education.
- Kotler, P., dan Keller, K. L. (2016). *Marketing Management (Fifth Edi)*. England: Pearson.
- Kotler, P & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management*. Upper Saddle River. NJ :Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Kotler, A. (2010). *Principles Of Marketing*. 13 Edition. In New Jersey . Upper Saddle River: Pearson Prentice Hall.
- Natalia Santoso, B. (2018). The Influence of Celebrity Endorsement in Social Media on Purchase Decision Through Perceived Value and Customer Attitude as Intervening Variabel in Souvenir Product in Surabaya. *Petra Business & Management Review*, 4(2), 134–147.

Ningsih, S., & Pradanawati, L. (2021). The Influence Of Brand Image, Price And Promotion On Purchase Decision (Case Study on Gea Geo Store). *Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR) Peer Reviewed-International Journal*, 5(3), 1-12. Retrieved from <https://jurnal.stie-aas.ac.id/index.php/IJEBAR>

Saparso, Soegeng Wahyoedi, & Santoso. (2021). The Role Of Brand Image In Mediating Service Quality And Promotion Towards Decisions To Buy Car On Credit In The Covid-19 Period (Study Case At Pt Maybank Indonesia Finance Dki Jakarta And Tangerang Branch). *International Journal of Science, Technology & Management*, 2(5), 1907-1917. doi: 10.46729/ijstm.v2i5.353

Suminto, S., Martati, I., Kusrihandayani, D., & Estiyani, E. (2022). The Analysis Effect of Brand Identity and Brand Image toward Brand Satisfaction and Brand Loyalty of Chocolate Product in Samarinda. *EDUTOURISM Journal Of Tourism Research*, 3(02), 197-205. doi: 10.53050/ejtr.v3i02.197

Tamara, S., Alie, J., & Wadud, M. (2021). The Effects of Brand Image and Price on Purchase Decision of Vivo Smartphones in Pampangan District. *International Journal of Marketing & Human Resource Research*, 2(1), 2746-4040.

Tsabitah, N., & Anggraeni, R. (2021). The Effect of Brand Image, Brand Personality and Brand Awareness on Purchase Intention of Local Fashion Brand "This Is April." *Kinerja*, 25(2), 234-250. doi: 10.24002/kinerja.v25i2.4701